

An efficient synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity of pyrimidine bearing 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives

B. Andrews* and Mansur Ahmed

PG & Research Department of Chemistry, Islamiah College (Affiliated to Thiruvalluvar University),
Vaniyambadi-635 752, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : bandrews2006@yahoo.com

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Abstract : A series of pyrimidine bearing 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have been synthesized and evaluated for antibacterial activity. All the structures of the newly synthesized compounds have been supported by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, GC-MS and CHN analysis. Most of the compounds have shown promising antibacterial activity when compared with the standard drug Ciprofloxacin.

Keywords : Pyrimidine, oxadiazole, carbothioamide, thiosemicarbazide, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Literature survey has revealed the importance of pyrimidine derivatives and antimicrobial agent¹, which are found to be associated with variety of biological activities such as insecticidal, antimicrobial, antiviral etc., pyrimidine derivatives²⁻⁸ are powerful C-C bond formation process has wide applications for the preparation of diverse aminoalkyl derivatives. It involves the condensation of a compound capable of supplying one or more active hydrogen atom with aldehyde and primary or secondary amine. Mannich bases are physiologically reactive because of the basic function rendering the molecule soluble in aqueous solvent when it is transformed into ammonium salt. Several medicinally useful Mannich bases have been reviewed by Tromontini and Angiolini⁹. Besides this, considerable work has been reported on synthesis and pharmacological activities of various Mannich bases for analogies, antispasmodic, anesthetic and antimalarial as well as intermediates in drug synthesis. Antiviral properties of certain thiourea and urea derivatives have been reported in which the antiviral effect is attributed to the presence of an intact NH-(C=S)-NH and NH-(C=O)-NH grouping¹⁰. In this direction the synthesis and pharmacological study of Mannich bases of 3- and 5-mercapto derivatives of 1,2,4-triazole have been reported in litera-

ture¹¹⁻¹⁶. Further, pyrimidine, fused heterocyclic pyrimidine derivatives and dihydropyrimidones are well known for their potential biological activity such as antiviral, antitumor, antimicrobial fungicide, algacide and as antibiotics¹⁷⁻²². Moreover the presences of different interacted functional groups determine their great synthetic potential. In continuation of this work, herein is reported that the synthesis and *in vitro* study of antibacterial activity of heterocyclic *N*-Mannich bases of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1*H*)-one (**3**) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram -ve), *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram -ve). Ciprofloxacin was used as standard drug. For this purpose, heterocyclic precursor DHPMs **1a-j** were synthesized by Biginelli reaction of aromatic aldehydes, ethylacetoacetate and thiourea according to the literature procedure. Subsequently, these DHPMs were used to synthesis compounds **2a-j**. All the synthesised compounds were characterized by using elemental analysis, mass spectras, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral studies.

Results and discussion

Compounds were synthesized as per the Scheme 1, where final compound **3** prepared by reacting carbothioamide compound **2** with NaOH with KI. 5-

Scheme 1. 5-(5-Amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (**3a**).

(Carbothioamide)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (**2**) were synthesized by reacting pyrimidine ethyl ester **1** with thiosemicarbazide in acetone followed by condensation reaction²³⁻²⁶. The pyrimidine ethyl ester compound **1** was prepared by reacting benzaldehyde, ethylacetoacetate and urea or thiourea in the presence of mineral acid followed by Biginelli reaction. The structures of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, GC-MS and CHN analysis (Table 1). Formation of compound **2** was confirmed by the presence of N-H stretching peaks at 3365, 3241 cm⁻¹ and 3116 cm⁻¹ and C=O stretching peaks at 1724 cm⁻¹ in IR and singlet at δ 6.50 for NH₂ group in ¹H NMR spectra. Treatment of compound **2** with NaOH

with KI, furnished 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (**3**).

The structure of **3** was elucidated on the basis of C-O-C linkage in the oxadiazole ring, which caused a sharp absorption band at 1020 cm⁻¹ in its IR spectrum. ¹H NMR spectrum showed a singlet at δ 3.98 due to NH₂ functionality confirmations of their structure were obtained through spectral and analytical data (Physical and analytical data are given in Table 2). IR and ¹H NMR spectral data revealed carbonyl absorption band at 1699 cm⁻¹ of NH-CO-NH group, N-N stretching band at 1089 cm⁻¹ aliphatic C-H and aromatic C-H stretching at 2978 cm⁻¹ and 3033 cm⁻¹ group of pyrimidine moiety **3**. Mass spectrum also supported the proposed structure by viewing molecular ion peak at *m/z* 271 M⁺.

All these compounds were screened for antibacterial activity by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram -ve), *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram -ve). Ciprofloxacin was used as standard drug. Most of the synthesized compounds showed moderate to good inhibition at 10 µg/ml concentration. However the activity was less compared to the standard drugs.

Experimental

Melting points were determined using open capillary method and are uncorrected. The compounds were checked for homogeneity by TLC on silica gel-G. The IR spectra were recorded on FT-IR Thermo Nicolet Avatar 370 spectrophotometer using KBr disc method. The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR were recorded on Bruker Avance III 400 MHz – FT NMR spectrophotometer using DMSO-*d*₆. Elemental analyses were recorded on Elemental Vario EL III. The mass spectrums were recorded on Joel GC-mate spectrometer. All compounds gave satisfactory micro analytical results. Pyrimidine **1** was prepared by reported method.

General procedure :

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (**2a**) :

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds **2a-j**, an equimolar mixture of compound **1** (0.01 mole) and thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mole) in acetone was refluxed

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of compounds **2a-j**

Sr. No.	Mol. formula	R	R ₁	X	Mol. wt.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)			
								C	N	H	S
2a	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S	H	H	O	305	85	140	51.17 (51.94)	22.50 (22.24)	4.94 (4.85)	10.47 (10.94)
2b	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ SCl	Cl	H	O	339	70	145	46.05 (46.30)	20.65 (20.94)	4.15 (4.60)	9.42 (9.49)
2c	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	O	348	78	170	52.35 (52.79)	24.42 (24.77)	5.84 (5.83)	9.28 (9.85)
2d	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ S	H	NO ₂	O	350	81	132	44.60 (44.06)	24.00 (24.07)	4.02 (4.43)	9.13 (9.22)
2e	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃ S	OH	H	O	321	83	160	48.62 (48.75)	21.18 (21.19)	4.70 (4.32)	9.95 (9.36)
2f	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₅ OS ₂	H	H	S	321	65	143	48.63 (48.46)	21.80 (21.97)	4.70 (4.55)	19.91 (20.10)
2g	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ OS ₂ Cl	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	S	355	72	110	43.90 (43.41)	19.72 (19.42)	3.97 (4.09)	18.00 (18.06)
2h	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₆ OS ₂	Cl	H	S	364	75	148	49.47 (49.00)	23.08 (23.26)	5.49 (5.22)	17.56 (17.69)
2i	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂	H	NO ₂	S	366	70	125	42.65 (42.59)	22.95 (23.00)	3.85 (3.54)	17.46 (17.72)
2j	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	OH	H	S	337	78	118	46.32 (46.53)	20.77 (21.03)	4.47 (4.70)	18.96 (19.06)

Table 2. Physical and analytical data of compounds **3a-j**

Sr. No.	Mol. formula	R	R ₁	X	Mol. wt.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)			
								C	N	H	S
3a	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂	H	H	O	271	89	176	57.52 (57.59)	25.80 (25.82)	4.07 (4.83)	0.00 (0.00)
3b	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	Cl	H	O	305	86	198	51.28 (51.07)	22.76 (22.95)	3.64 (3.96)	0.00 (0.00)
3c	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	O	314	88	205	57.51 (57.34)	26.71 (26.75)	5.25 (5.77)	0.00 (0.00)
3d	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₄	H	NO ₂	O	316	73	136	49.89 (49.39)	26.46 (26.82)	3.86 (3.82)	0.00 (0.00)
3e	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃	OH	H	O	287	84	125	54.10 (54.38)	24.95 (24.38)	4.57 (4.56)	0.00 (0.00)
3f	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₅ OS	H	H	S	287	80	190	54.23 (54.38)	24.52 (24.39)	4.55 (4.56)	11.00 (11.13)
3g	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₆ OS	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	S	330	78	148	48.81 (48.62)	21.97 (21.80)	3.24 (3.76)	10.33 (9.95)
3h	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₅ OSCl	Cl	H	S	321	81	183	54.01 (54.57)	25.29 (25.45)	5.80 (5.49)	10.03 (9.68)
3i	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₃ S	H	NO ₂	S	332	76	180	47.87 (47.02)	25.08 (25.30)	3.47 (3.64)	9.96 (9.62)
3j	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S	OH	H	S	303	82	172	51.69 (51.52)	23.19 (23.16)	4.22 (4.32)	10.26 (10.54)

for 10–12 h and allowed to cool and yellow solid was recrystallized from alcohol. Melting point of the compound is 140 °C, yield 85%.

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.251 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.152 (1H, d, J 3.2 Hz, CH), 6.501 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.213–7.336 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.702 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz, NH), 8.175 (2H, d, J 6.4 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.149 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 17.72, 59.17, 99.33, 126.21, 127.23, 128.34, 148.25, 151.71, 152.16, 165.33, 178.40; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3365, 3241, 3116 (NH), 3079 (Ar-H), 2978 (CH), 1724 (C=O), 1598 (C=N), 1385 (C-N), 1219 (C=S), 1089 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [305 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (2b) :

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.251 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.146 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 6.530 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.239–7.260 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 7.377–7.399 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 7.733 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz, NH), 8.096 (2H, d, J 2 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.204 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 17.75, 59.22, 98.87, 128.15, 128.34, 131.74, 143.74, 148.64, 151.92, 165.18, 178.43; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3376, 3240, 3118 (NH), 3029 (Ar-H), 2978 (CH), 1724 (C=O), 1597 (C=N), 1340 (C-N), 1220 (C=S), 1090 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [339 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(4-(dimethylamino)-phenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (2c) :

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.226 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.846 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 5.503 (1H, d, J 3.2 Hz, CH), 6.130 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.650 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.036 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.534 (2H, d, J 2.8 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.036 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz, NH), 9.866 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 17.67, 53.29, 59.06, 99.93, 112.20, 126.85, 132.61, 149.73, 151.27, 165.46, 178.43; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3365, 3241, 3116 (NH), 3053 (Ar-H), 2978 (CH), 1724 (C=O), 1598 (C=N), 1340 (C-N), 1219 (C=S), 1089 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [349 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (2d) :

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.276 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.309

(1H, d, J 4 Hz, CH), 6.970 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.656–7.760 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.826 (2H, d, J 3.7 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.345 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, NH), 9.872 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 17.81, 58.61, 98.35, 129.61, 130.19, 132.95, 147.65, 147.73, 149.36, 151.62, 151.73, 165.04, 178.44; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3377, 3239, 3117 (NH), 3029 (Ar-H), 2977 (CH), 1719 (C=O), 1561 (C=N), 1365 (C-N), 1219 (C=S), 1091 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [350 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (2e) :

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.233 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.049 (1H, d, J 3.2 Hz, CH), 6.176 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.676–6.698 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 7.019–7.040 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 7.572 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 7.956 (1H, s, OH), 9.065 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz, NH), 9.868 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 17.69, 59.07, 99.80, 114.96, 127.37, 135.40, 151.66, 152.19, 156.50, 165.39, 178.43; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3515 (OH), 3377, 3234, 3151 (NH), 2997 (Ar-H), 2904 (CH), 1684 (C=O), 1596 (C=N), 1367 (C-N), 1268 (C=S), 1098 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [321 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (2f) :

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.292 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.176 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 6.681 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.211–7.366 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.981 (2H, d, J 4 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.887 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz, NH), 10.308 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 17.47, 59.54, 100.75, 126.35, 127.62, 128.50, 143.47, 144.95, 165.10, 178.47, 183.94; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3328, 3172, 3106 (NH), 2979 (Ar-H), 2936 (CH), 1669 (C=O), 1573 (C=N), 1327 (C-N), 1283 (C=S), 1117 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [321 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (2g) :

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.296 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.174 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, CH), 7.023 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.209–7.243 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 7.413–7.503 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 8.295 (2H, d, J 0.8 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.648 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz, NH), 10.363 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 17.48, 59.63, 100.34, 128.27, 128.52, 142.33, 145.28, 164.96,

178.43, 183.89; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3377, 3327, 3236 (NH), 3158 (Ar-H), 2996 (CH), 1731 (C=O), 1596 (C=N), 1335 (C-N), 1281 (C=S), 1041 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [355 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(4-(dimethylamino)-phenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (2h) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.277 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.855 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 5.048 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, CH), 6.305 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.663 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.016 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 9.509 (2H, d, J 1.6 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.887 (1H, s, NH), 10.197 (1H, d, J 0.8 Hz, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.48, 53.53, 59.43, 101.27, 112.16, 127.08, 131.19, 149.93, 151.56, 165.25, 178.47, 183.93; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3377, 3356, 3168 (NH), 3105 (Ar-H), 2981 (CH), 1669 (C=O), 1577 (C=N), 1366 (C-N), 1285 (C=S), 1117 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [364 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (2i) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.498 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.931 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz, CH), 6.557 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.540–7.817 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.178 (2H, d, J 0.8 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 8.566 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, NH), 9.855 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.49, 60.26, 98.35, 122.96, 123.05, 129.73, 135.27, 141.64, 149.51, 151.64, 168.09, 175.39, 183.85; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3379, 3273, 3175 (NH), 3088 (Ar-H), 2982 (CH), 1727 (C=O), 1530 (C=N), 1315 (C-N), 1233 (C=S), 1117 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [366 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(carbothioamide)-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (2j) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.277 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.063 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 6.120 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.699–6.720 (2H, t, Ar-H), 6.999–7.070 (2H, q, Ar-H), 7.500 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.965 (2H, d, J 3.5 Hz, $\text{NH} \times 2$), 9.528 (1H, d, J 1.6 Hz, NH), 9.883 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.50, 59.47, 101.12, 115.17, 127.61, 134.08, 144.42, 151.68, 165.18, 178.38, 183.83; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3429 (OH), 3245, 3179, 3079 (NH), 3036 (Ar-H), 2988 (CH), 1715 (C=O), 1597 (C=N), 1314 (C-N), 1259 (C=S), 1082 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [337 M^+].

General procedure for synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3a) :

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds **3a-j**, carbothioamide (**2**) (0.01 mole) was added into 10% NaOH with cooling and shaking. Then iodine solution in KI was added gradually and shaking until the iodine color persisted. This reaction mixture was heated continuously for 5 h and it was concentrated the residue, its cooled and poured onto ice cold water. This solution was filtered and acidified with 10% HCl to isolate the product. It was filtered washed with cold water and little amount of CS_2 was added. The product was recrystallized from alcohol. m.p. 176 $^\circ\text{C}$, yield 89%.

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.264 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.987 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.167 (1H, d, J 3.2 Hz, CH), 7.245–7.347 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.717 (1H, d, J 1.6 Hz, NH), 9.165 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.73, 59.14, 99.29, 126.22, 127.21, 128.33, 142.03, 144.83, 148.28, 152.14, 165.31; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3375, 3242, 3115 (NH), 3033 (Ar-H), 2978 (CH), 1699 (C=O), 1598 (C=N), 1340 (C-N), 1089 (N-N), 1020 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [271 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3b) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.255 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.997 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.152 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 7.243–7.299 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.735 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz, NH), 9.207 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.76, 59.21, 98.85, 128.15, 128.34, 131.77, 143.76, 148.65, 151.94, 165.17; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3376, 3244, 3116 (NH), 2980 (Ar-H), 2956 (CH), 1700 (C=O), 1534 (C=N), 1367 (C-N), 1170 (C-O), 1087 (N-N); GCMS : (m/z) [305 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(4-(dimethylamino)phenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3c) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.227 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.848 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.986 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.038 (1H, d, J 4.4 Hz, CH), 6.658 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.022–7.058 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.539 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz, NH), 9.041 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.68,

53.28, 59.05, 99.89, 112.29, 126.86, 132.76, 134.25, 147.50, 149.65, 152.25, 165.46; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3380, 3245, 3114 (NH), 2953 (Ar-H), 2811 (CH), 1719 (C=O), 1560 (C=N), 1384 (C-N), 1091 (N-N), 1025 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [314 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3d) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.283 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.039 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.314 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 7.699–8.142 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.722 (1H, d, J 10.4 Hz, NH), 9.310 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.81, 59.35, 98.35, 122.26, 130.10, 130.14, 132.94, 146.96, 147.70, 148.30, 149.35, 151.77, 165.02; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3566, 3440, 3335 (NH), 3090 (Ar-H), 2966 (CH), 1707 (C=O), 1526 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1088 (N-N), 1007 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [316 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3e) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.286 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.046 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.100 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 6.765–7.793 (2H, q, Ar-H), 7.013–7.033 (2H, q, Ar-H), 9.187 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz, NH), 9.347 (1H, s, NH), 10.296 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.69, 59.07, 99.78, 114.96, 127.36, 135.41, 136.72, 148.10, 151.98, 152.17, 165.25; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3291 (OH), 3218, 3121 (NH), 3021 (Ar-H), 2981 (CH), 1692 (C=O), 1514 (C=N), 1316 (C-N), 1101 (N-N), 1023 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [287 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (3f) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.304 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.029 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.191 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 7.224–7.373 (5H, m, Ar-H), 9.634 (1H, d, J 1.6 Hz, NH), 10.314 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.13, 59.54, 100.76, 126.36, 127.62, 128.49, 143.48, 144.95, 165.11, 174.28; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3328, 3172 (NH), 3072 (Ar-H), 2979 (CH), 1573 (C=N), 1370 (C-N), 1197 (C=S), 1117 (N-N), 1027 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [287 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (3g) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.297 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.022 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.171 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 7.222–7.258 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 7.424–7.453 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 9.645 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, NH), 10.361 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.15, 59.61, 100.33, 128.27, 128.52, 128.63, 128.87, 142.35, 145.30, 164.96, 174.28; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3437, 3327, 3171 (NH), 3104 (Ar-H), 2982 (CH), 1573 (C=N), 1334 (C-N), 1197 (C=S), 1092 (N-N), 1030 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [321 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(4-(dimethylamino)phenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (3h) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.285 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.933 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.018 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.104 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 7.022 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.114–7.463 (2H, m, Ar-H), 9.561 (1H, d, J 1.6 Hz, NH), 10.253 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.11, 53.44, 59.52, 100.93, 127.34, 130.33, 144.66, 148.47, 151.67, 155.19, 165.17, 174.03; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3482, 3326, 3173 (NH), 3032 (Ar-H), 2981 (CH), 1576 (C=N), 1329 (C-N), 1182 (C=S), 1117 (N-N), 1022 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [330 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (3i) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.323 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.033 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.339 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, CH), 7.663–7.696 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 8.081–8.242 (3H, m, Ar-H), 9.757 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz, NH), 10.493 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 17.19, 59.75, 99.86, 121.12, 122.66, 130.36, 132.97, 145.47, 145.94, 147.80, 164.82, 174.52; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3437, 3179 (NH), 3027 (Ar-H), 2988 (CH), 1532 (C=N), 1344 (C-N), 1189 (C=S), 1102 (N-N), 1039 (C-O); GCMS : (m/z) [332 M^+].

Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-6-methyl-4-phenylpyrimidin-2(1H)-thione (3j) :

^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 2.279 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.994 (2H, s, NH_2), 5.066 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 6.701–6.722

(2H, dd, Ar-H), 7.002–7.033 (2H, dd, Ar-H), 9.402 (1H, s, OH), 9.526 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, NH), 10.216 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 17.09, 59.46, 101.13, 115.12, 127.61, 134.09, 144.43, 156.86, 165.18, 173.87; FT-IR (cm⁻¹) : 3477 (OH), 3325, 3171, 3104 (NH), 2985 (Ar-H), 2903 (CH), 1597 (C=N), 1315 (C-N), 1196 (C=S), 1083 (N-N), 1027 (C-O); GCMS : (*m/z*) [303 M⁺].

Antibacterial studies :

Among the newly synthesized pyrimidine derivatives were screened for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against the species of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, using agar well disk diffusion method. The test compounds were dissolved in DMSO to get a solution of 10 µg/ml concentration. The inhibition zones were measured in millimeters at the end of an incubation period of 18 h at 37 °C. Ciprofloxacin was used as a reference standard and the results were shown in Table 3. Most of the tested compounds showed antibacterial activity comparable with that of the standard drug Ciprofloxacin.

Table 3. Antibacterial activities of compounds **3a-j**

Compd.	Antibacterial activity in (mm); Std. Ciprofloxacin (25 mm)		
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (Gram-ve)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (Gram+ve)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (Gram-ve)
Control	0	0	0
3a	4 mm	-	-
3b	4 mm	-	-
3c	-	-	-
3d	6 mm	5 mm	6 mm
3e	10 mm	8 mm	9 mm
3f	-	-	-
3g	9 mm	8 mm	10 mm
3h	12 mm	10 mm	7 mm
3i	9 mm	6 mm	6 mm
3j	15 mm	14 mm	12 mm

Concentration was 10 µg/ml @ 10% DMSO; ‘-’ and ‘0’ no inhibition zone.

The investigation of antibacterial screening data revealed that all the tested compounds showed moderate to good inhibition at 10 µg/ml concentration. Especially the compounds **3e**, **3h** and **3j** showed very good activity than

the others. However the activity was less compared to the standard drug.

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